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MED-GOLD

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**Live and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable D6.22

SUMMARY OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES N.2

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Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MED-GOLD project, which aims to demonstrate the proof-of-concept on how climate services can make European agriculture and food systems more competitive, resilient and efficient through three case studies in the olive, grape and durum wheat sectors.

The dissemination and communication work tries to maximize the impact of the project's results through different channels and target audiences, as is described in the MED-GOLD deliverable D7.1 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan" [RD. 2]. This deliverable synthesises all the communication and dissemination activities performed during this second year of activity.

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (GA, Part B Table 1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot climate services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE

A comprehensive and communal strategy on communication, dissemination and exploitation of the MED-GOLD project is required for a wide adoption of the project by the different target audiences. At this stage of the project, most of the work has been concentrated on defining and designing the core tools and technologies to be developed.

This document, as it is established on the MED-GOLD grant agreement, collects all contributions performed by the partners through the different tasks that have been carried out during the second year of the project, either on setting the corresponding channels or disseminating the project characteristics and advances. This description of communication and dissemination activities corresponds to the period M13-M24.

1.2. SCOPE

The scope of this deliverable is to present a yearly report related to the dissemination and communication activities performed by project partners, either on a collaborative approach or on their individual active roles. Communication and dissemination objectives and strategy performed is described as a summary of the activities that were undertaken on the reporting period.

To ensure that all communication and dissemination (C&D) activities have been properly logged, we employed the procedure described in deliverable D7.1 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD. 2] and MED-GOLD Quality Plan [RD. 3]. In this way, all the activities were centralised in a spreadsheet that forms the basis of this report that also follows the structure of the deliverable 6.7 "Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities N.1" [RD.7]. This document could be considered as an update that includes the progress in C&D activities.

1.3. DEFINITIONS AND ACRONYMS

1.3.1. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Communication	Strategic and targeted measures for promoting the results to a multitude of audiences
Dissemination	Public disclosure of the results by an appropriate communication channel.
Exploitation	Use of the results during and after the project's implementation. It can be for commercial purposes, improving policies and tackling economic and societal problems.

1.3.2. ACRONYM AND INITIALISM

Acronyms and initialisms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2 Acronyms and Initialisms

Acronym	Definition
%	Percentage
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CGIAR	Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research
CIMMYT	International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change
CO	Colombia
CONF	Conference
COP	Conference of the Parties
CREA	Council for Agricultural Research and Economics
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ECCA	European Climate Change Adaptation

Acronym	Definition
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GFCFS	Global Framework for Climate Services
GP	General Public
GR	Greece
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IT	Italy
JPI	Joint Programming Initiative
PR	Professional public
PT	Portugal
ROI	Region of Interest
SP	Spain
UMNG	Nueva Granada Military University
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WS	Workshop

2. REFERENCES

2.1. REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 2-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Date
[RD.1]	MED-GOLD Grant Agreement	2017
[RD.2]	Deliverable 7.1. MED-GOLD Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan V2.2	2019
[RD.3]	MED-GOLD Quality Plan	2018
[RD.4]	Deliverable 6.1. Climate related Initiatives Interactions Report 1	2018
[RD.5]	Milestone 2. MED-GOLD community developed	2018
[RD.6]	Milestone 3. Report on the MED-GOLD mailing list	2018
[RD.7]	D6.7 Summary of dissemination and communication activities n°1	2018
[RD.8]	D5.1 Report on the status of the MED-GOLD Community	2018
[RD.9]	D6.11 Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report n.2	2019
[RD.10]	D6.5 Compilation of Publications Abstracts n.1	2019

3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORTING PERIOD

A number of different objectives and tasks related to communication and dissemination were established within the MED-GOLD Grant Agreement, especially in Work Package 6 “Communication and exploitation of the MED-GOLD value chain” [RD.1]. Deliverable 7.1, “MED-GOLD Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan” [RD.2], describes the development and implementation of the appropriate dissemination, communication strategy and related activities.

Different responsibilities have been defined to ensure that each partner contributes to the C&D strategies. A monitoring system was adopted for to control programmed activities, detect opportunities and analyze weaknesses.

The description of activities and mechanisms used since the last period and the analysis of the results of the implemented actions are the main objective of this report.

Taking advantage of the available tools for analyzing traffic on websites and social media (twitter), one of the objectives of this report is oriented to understanding the behavior of the MED-GOLD website and its social media account during the last period. Also, to have both quantitative and qualitative measures that allow us to stablish the approach of activities that requires the presence of partners, stakeholders and the general public, such as workshops or trainings that are part of C&D activities.

We have assessed the results obtained by the adoption of strategies in C&D which are oriented to increase brand awareness, to drive traffic to the MED-GOLD website, reinforce the communication strategies, increase the number of visits to the project website, update the design of the website, and improve the temporal activities in social media channels.

4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND ACTIVITIES

Summary of the channels defined and implemented and the C&D activities performed during the second year (M13-M24).

4.1. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATIONS CHANNELS

In this section, the channels used as communication platform for the diffusion of messages and relevant information out of the limits of the MED-GOLD consortium are described. This information is oriented to engage the general public, researchers, professional public, etc. to be part of the MED-GOLD community as part of the strategy exposed in the milestone2 "MED-GOLD community developed" [RD.5].

4.1.1. MED-GOLD WEBSITE

The MED-GOLD website (www.med-gold.eu) was launched on February 7th 2018 and has been modified 24 times since it was launched demonstrating an important activity related with design, updating, translations, news, etc. .

An internal review of the web-site characteristics has been conducted in order to enhance some of the functionalities and improve the overall readability and effectiveness of the web-site as a communication tool. The main changes are being implemented at the time of the present report, are listed below.

- In the homepage (<https://www.med-gold.eu>) the running slides is updated to advertise the infosheets that are now available in all languages.
- In the homepage (<https://www.med-gold.eu>) an extra tab for "Community" added next to the existing ones, if possible, where the expected roles of the MED-GOLD community members are clearly explained, as well as what is NOT expected from them, plus the potential benefits for them joining the community (as these questions came quite frequently so far)
- Related projects (<https://www.med-gold.eu/project/#relatedprojects>) is updated according to the content of DEL6.11 [RD.9]
- The list of scientific papers (<https://www.med-gold.eu/documents-publications/>) is updated according to the content of DEL6.5 [RD.10]
- The list of articles/interviews (<https://www.med-gold.eu/documents-publications/>) is updated according to the content of table 4-3 of this document.

Several other required changes have been identified in order better align all multi-language versions of the website, including: a) translation of the workplan scheme (<https://www.med-gold.eu/project/#workplan>); systematic translation of all infosheets (<https://www.med-gold.eu/documents-publications/>); translation of the brochure (<https://www.med-gold.eu/media/>); translation of all MED-GOLD events (<https://www.med-gold.eu/events-news/>).

The figure 4.1 depicts relevant dates in which the MED-GOLD website has suffered modifications mainly in design and internal applications as well as updates in different languages.

Figure 4-1. MED-GOLD website evolution.

The most periodically updated sections are related with **Last News** and **Events** due to the activities of dissemination and communication realized by the sectors involved in the MED-GOLD project.

Figure 4-2. MED-GOLD Latest news Section

Table 4-1 depicts the changes in the internal structure of the web site, reinforcing the idea that the main content is oriented to visual information (infosheets, news, events)

Table 4-1. MED-GOLD website content changes.

Content Type	captures	URLs	URL 2018
image/png	165	145	21
application/javascript	102	61	18
text/css	51	33	7
text/html	28	18	7
application/json	25	21	7
image/jpeg	24	21	7
application/octet-stream	20	14	3
application/vnd.ms-fontobject	11	8	3
image/svg+xml	10	7	2
application/font-woff	9	7	2
image/gif	8	8	8
image/vnd.microsoft.icon	4	2	1
text/calendar	2	1	0

This reported analysis of the website activity has been realized using Google Analytics during the period between the first report D6.7 October 31st, 2018 and 28st November 5th, 2019.

Figure 4.3 shows a total of 2.829 users of the MED-GOLD website up to November 5th 2019. The most representative month with 517 connected users was October 2019; coinciding with General Assembly. The average time of the connection is approximately 2 min and 40 seconds, indicating that the interaction between user and website is acceptable considering that currently there are no interactive tools implemented in the website. An interesting statistic is that 88% of the users connected during this period corresponded to new users. The traffic derived from social media or referred from other sources is approximately 55%, indicating that an extra effort motivating the users to access the website from social media channels is necessary. Twitter redirects almost the 65% of social media channel.

Figure 4-3. MED-GOLD website users.

The geographical distribution of users is shown in Figure 4-4. The top five countries indicate that most interest in the project is located in Europe and North America. Italy contributes with 24.6%, followed by US with 23%, Spain with 7%, Portugal with 6.5% and the United Kingdom with 1.5%. It is relevant to highlight that the Southern European countries contribute with 42% of users, this being an expected result due to the area of interest of the MED-GOLD project.

According to demographics data extracted from Google Analytics, it is interesting to observe that 61% of visitors are less than 34 years old, indicating a relevant interest in the project among the population commonly described as young.

Figure 4-4. MED-GOLD visitor's distribution by country.

At this point, it is important to highlight that the MED-GOLD website is available in six languages (English, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Greek and French). This allows to cover an important geographical area not only focused on Europe but also at the international level. This strategy is critical considering that one of the objectives of the MED-GOLD project is to reach different markets, for example Latin America and Africa.

4.1.2. MED-GOLD MAILING LISTS

The MED-GOLD mailing list is one of the most useful tool for the creation and consolidation of the MED-GOLD community as it was explained in the milestone3 “Report on the MED-GOLD mailing list” [RD.6]. The MED-GOLD community consists of both public and private European and national organisations involved in different aspects related to the three agricultural sectors targeted under MED-GOLD: olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta. Emailing an introductory presentation about MED-GOLD, was an immediate action taken to engage organisations to be part of the community.

The development of the MED-GOLD community started considering organisations connected with MED-GOLD industrial partners in Spain (DCOOP), Portugal (SOGRAPE) and Italy (Barilla). Also organisations that operate at European level were identified as well as a number of relevant European projects and initiatives [RD.8]. Organisations derived from the market analysis were approached and informed about the option to subscribe to the mailing list. In addition, direct contact with key European organisations (e.g. networks, associations, private companies including SMEs) operating in the MED-GOLD targeted sectors is currently being pursued. These organisations will act as multiplier organisations and as an entry point to other climate service end-users operating in the three targeted sectors.

Currently 152 organisations have been identified and included into the MED-GOLD contacts’ database, including organisations operating at the European, national and local levels and covering relevant stakeholders in the olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta sectors, agriculture in general and the climate services sector.

New strategies have been adopted for engaging new users to be part of the MED-GOLD community: reaching out potential end-user communities through social media (Figure 4.-5), national media in partner countries (specialized magazines for all the 3 sectors), attending end-user centred events and the inclusion of a call to join the MED-GOLD community as slides included in presentations done by partners.

Figure 4-5. MED-GOLD posts in Facebook related groups.

4.1.3. MED-GOLD SOCIAL NETWORKS

In May 2019, D7.1 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan” was updated and a specific annex for a social network strategy was added.

Twitter is a social network which enables users to send short messages to the general public but also to specific stakeholders. Moreover, it is also a channel through which interaction with other initiatives can be followed and new results and announcements can be rapidly updated. A twitter profile (@medgold_h2020) was created in November 2017 for project dissemination (Figure 4-7). Figure 4-6 shows an increasing behaviour in Twitter followers for the @medgold_h2020 account from December 2017 to September 2019.

Figure 4-6. MED-GOLD Twitter follower evolution.

The main statistics on 5th November, 2019:

Number of posts: 344 tweets

Followers: 299

Following: 607

Figure 4-7. MED-GOLD Twitter account.

The impression in Twitter shows the number of times that user saw a tweet. The Figure 4-8 shows the impressions caused by tweets in August 2019. This result indicates that, information related with training or the MED-GOLD services provokes most interest in the users.

med-gold @medgold_h2020 · Aug 19 #HappyMonday! We are looking for experts in the #agriculture sector to build the MED-GOLD community - a network where we can all mutually benefit from each other's knowledge & experience. 🙌 Join us! med-gold.eu/participate/ pic.twitter.com/qfll0Gy1fS <small>View Tweet activity</small>	1,056	32	3.0%
med-gold @medgold_h2020 · Aug 12 #HappyMonday! 🎉👨🍳 Have you heard about our upcoming events? Learn more about the next MED-GOLD #GeneralAssembly 2019 and #SummerSchool 2020 in Cagliari here: med-gold.eu/events-news/ pic.twitter.com/8ZlKj5jy9 <small>View Tweet activity</small>	377	15	4.0%
med-gold @medgold_h2020 · Aug 5 #HappyMonday! Discover here the WHY - WHAT - HOW of the MED-GOLD project: med-gold.eu/project/#descr... pic.twitter.com/o4DYHp2DUQ <small>View Tweet activity</small>	378	13	3.4%
med-gold @medgold_h2020 · Aug 5 Starting to plan the MED-GOLD SUMMER SCHOOL 2020 🎓 🌱 Turning climate information into value for traditional Mediterranean agri-food systems. 🙌 Stay tuned for next updates! med-gold.eu/event/summer-s... <small>View Tweet activity</small>	1,334	23	1.7%

Figure 4-8. Tweet impressions during August 2019.

In a general view, the Twitter Analytics tool indicated that the most relevant tweet corresponds to November 14th 2018 (Figure 4-9) when the first infosheet was launched. According to the twitter activity report, the trend of impressions has grown linearly from March 2019, coinciding with the adoption of new strategies in social media management. The trend of “Likes” is also growing following a similar trend to impressions.

Figure 4-9. MED-GOLD most impressed tweet.

The Facebook account (Figure 4-10) has been used mainly in the dissemination of the MED-GOLD services among different groups related with the olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta sectors.

Figure 4-10. MED-GOLD Facebook account.

4.1.4. MED-GOLD NEWSLETTERS

The newsletter is another important source of communication implemented in the MED-GOLD project and initially oriented to the MED-GOLD community. Two newsletters have been published since December 2018 using the email as main dissemination tool. The newsletters are available in the MED-GOLD website.

The first newsletter was published in December 2018 (Figure 4-11) and sent by email to the MED-GOLD community. The content was focused on “Perspectives of user engagement activities” and included different sections as:

- Project description
- Analysis of the feedback collected through the focus groups and workshop organised by Work Package 2, 3 and 4 that were conducted between May and June 2018.
- Announcement of upcoming activities and the active participation of MED-GOLD partners in conferences, workshops and congresses in the past and coming months

Figure 4-11. MED-GOLD general view of first newsletter

The second newsletter was published in June 2019 (Figure 4-12). It was also sent by email to the MED-GOLD community participants with registered interest. The main content of this publication was the 'Development of sectoral tools and mutual understanding' and included the following sections: a brief description of identification of end user needs for three sector involved in the project olive/olive oil, grape/wine and durum wheat/pasta trough workshops organised during the first semester of this year. Other sections included were:

- An announcement related to the availability of the MED-GOLD website in different languages.
- An announcement about the MED-GOLD forum.
- Presentation of the infosheet for olive/olive oil and durum wheat/pasta sectors.
- Information about the availability of material from the webinar on climate services and its value into the Mediterranean wine sector.
- The presence of the MED-GOLD project on the Portuguese TV.
- Events with MED-GOLD presence since December 2018 (when the previous newsletter was published) and coming events
- Information on new publications.

Figure 4-12. MED-GOLD general view of second newsletter

4.1.5. MED-GOLD INFOSHEET

Three infosheets have been published so far describing climate services for olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta. The objective of the infosheets is to describe in a simple way the type of climate services that the project will provide at different time scales. Moreover, and since the target group for this information are end-users that may not be familiar with climate concepts, a glossary has been included.

The first infosheet on climate services for grape/wine was published in November 2018 (Figure 4-13). In June 2019, a second infosheet focusing on the olive and olive oil sector and a third infosheet for the durum wheat/pasta sector (Figure 4-14) were published (Figure 4-15). They are being translated into all the MED-GOLD languages.

Grape and wine production is heavily affected by weather and climate, thereby is highly vulnerable to climate change. MED-GOLD will propose climate services deploying forecast information at the medium (next 6 months) and long-term (next 30 years). This information will be provided at higher spatial resolution than what is currently available. To provide the highest value for decision-making, the services will be co-developed with professional users from the sector.

Wine producers face diverse challenges affecting several decision processes in their business, such as strategic definitions, viticulture, oenological and stock management. Some examples are presented below to show how climate services - in this case, predictions of climate variables and bioclimatic indices - can improve decision-making and win over challenges posed by climate variability and climate change.

Time scale	Decision area	Challenge	MED-GOLD climate service	Benefits
Long-term (30 years)	Long-term strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Purchase of new vineyards and/or selection of future new locations. Choice of grape varieties, rootstocks and vineyard design. Anticipation of needs to change wine style. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Precipitation Growing season average temperature Warm spell duration index Growing degree days Number of heat stress days Spring total precipitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indication of areas with suitable climate to meet production and quality goals for the next decades. Matching adequate grape varieties and rootstocks to expected climate. Identification of likely moment with adverse climate for current wine style.
Medium-term (6 months)	Viticulture management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better pruning and canopy management. Improve planning of treatments and harvest setting with higher accuracy. Better labour management, operational subcontracting and environmental protection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Precipitation Growing season average temperature Warm spell duration index Growing degree days Number of heat stress days Spring total precipitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Longer anticipation of best timing for vineyard operations. Identification of time periods with high-demand for labour and inputs. Schedule of best moments for treatments with higher temporal precision.
	Oenological management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better maturation control planning. Improve harvest efficiency. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of likely moments for veraison and harvest. Timely anticipation of adverse conditions.
	Stock management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve supplier negotiation. Better prices and supply chain. Marketing and promotions. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anticipation of seasonal climate trends with adequate temporal and spatial resolution.

Planning of plant protection treatments

Several diseases affecting grapevines are favoured by specific climatic conditions. These diseases may be of fungal origin, namely downy and powdery mildew, among others, and of bacterial origin or caused by pests, namely insects. Fungal diseases occur when the plant, being a carrier, is exposed to favourable climatic conditions such as high humidity and mild-warm temperatures, which associated to poor aeration promote their development. When emerging at critical phenological stages, these diseases damage grapes, ultimately reducing yields and resulting in a loss of wine quality.

Currently, SOGRAPE (MED-GOLD's champion user for the wine sector) uses 4 to 5-day lead-time forecasts to schedule their spraying while avoiding product loss from subsequent rainfall. This anticipation of vineyard protection planning results in important, sustainable benefits. Medium-term decisions are currently undertaken with reference to past average conditions, both intuitively and using 30-year climate data series available from the national weather service.

Advantages of having access to medium-term (seasonal) climate predictions:

- Efficient management of spraying against diseases**, supporting vineyard development or inducing grapevine's resistance against humidity-driven diseases (fungal) in more sensitive phenological states.
- Efficient stock management** to be prepared in advance to avoid higher prices and stock disruptions.
- Accurate setting of harvest dates**, which is influenced by adverse conditions, namely pests risk.

Glossary

Climate services: transformation of climate-related data and other information into customized products such as trends, economic analysis, advice on best practices, and any other climate-related service liable to benefit that may be of use for the society

Weather forecasts: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables for the next hours and days (up to two weeks)

Climate predictions: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables that extend further into the future than weather forecasts, from months and seasons up to decades

Seasonal predictions: climate predictions for the next season. These predictions can be provided for the next 6 months

Climate projections: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables that extend even further into the future than climate predictions, from decades up to centuries

Growing season average temperature (GST): average of daily average temperatures between April 1st and October 31st (Northern Hemisphere)

Growing degree days (GDD): sum of daily differences between daily temperature averages and 10°C (vegetative growth minimum temperature) between April 1st and October 31st (Northern Hemisphere)

Spring total precipitation (SprR): total rainfall from April 21st to June 21st (Northern Hemisphere)

Number of heat stress days (SU35): annual count of days when daily maximum temperatures exceed 35°C

Warm spell duration index (WSDI): annual count of days with at least 6 consecutive days when the daily maximum temperature exceeds its 90th percentile

About MED-GOLD

MED-GOLD. Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional Mediterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems, is a 4-year project contributing to make European agriculture and food systems more resilient, sustainable and efficient in the face of climate change by using climate services to minimize climate-driven risks/costs and seize opportunities for added value

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776467

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Figure 4-13. Grape/Wine infosheet

CLIMATE SERVICES FOR THE OLIVE AND OLIVE OIL SECTOR

Olive and olive oil production is heavily affected by weather and climate, and is thereby highly vulnerable to climate change. MED-GOLD will use a range of tools to support decision-making in the olive and olive oil sector over a range of timescales, from months to decades. These tools will include climatic indices, numerical models, and agroecosystem analyses to turn climate and other data into customized products. This process of turning climate-related information into products with added value for decision-making is called climate service. Climate information underlying the services will be provided at higher spatial resolution and with less bias than currently available.

Olive and olive oil producers face a variety of climate-related challenges in the long, medium and short term that need to be tackled by climate-informed decision-making. Some of the main challenges are presented below, with an indication of how the related decisions can be optimized using appropriate climate services tools that support a long-term strategy as well as shorter-term agricultural and commercial management.

Time scale	Decision type	Challenges	MED-GOLD climate services tools	Benefits
Short-term (e.g., 30 days)	Agro-management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimize pest treatments Optimize irrigation planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Precipitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce pest damage while protecting the environment Optimize the use of water resources
	Quality management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better estimate pest affection and frost damages Correct olive formation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Numerical modelling of pests and evapotranspiration Insolation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimize olive and olive oil quality
Mid-term (e.g., 6 months)	Agro-management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimize fertilization planning Optimize irrigation planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Precipitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainability Optimization of the use of fertilizers
	Stock management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better estimation of olive production Improve the selling process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Numerical modelling of productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve stock and selling planning
Long-term (e.g., 10-20 years)	Long-term strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Select production areas Decide type of exploitation (traditional, intensive, etc.) Select tree spacing, varieties, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature and precipitation patterns Bioclimatic indices (see glossary): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mean summer max. temperature Mean winter min. temperature Num. of winter cold days Num. of annual & spring heat days Num. of summer heat days Total annual, summer & winter precipitation Num. of annual & winter dry days Numerical modelling of pests and productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Future productivity per geographical area Regional recommendations for improved crop management strategy Cost-benefit analysis per productivity area Exploitation adaptation and investment evaluation

Control of olive fruit fly (*Bactrocera oleae*)

Olive fruit fly is the major pest of commercial olives worldwide and its dynamics is strongly linked to both olive fruit development and the local climate, with mild temperatures and medium to high air humidity being especially favorable. In Andalusia (Spain), adult flies first emerge in spring and attack olives remaining on trees from the previous season, but damage typically starts in summer (usually in mid-July). When pits begin to harden, fly eggs are laid in olive fruits, and larvae that hatch from these eggs cause direct damage by feeding on olive fruit pulp. Larval feeding also causes indirect damage by both inducing fruit drop and allowing microorganisms to invade the fruit, which results in increased acidity and lowered quality and value of olive oil (losses can be up to 80%).

Currently, olive producers advised by DCOOP (MED-GOLD's champion user for the olive sector) use traps with sex-pheromones or diammonium phosphate food bait to monitor olive fruit fly. To control this pest, they apply phytosanitary treatments as well as other less common methods such as biological control.

Advantages of having access to mid-term (seasonal) climate predictions:

1. Identification of regions at risk for olive fruit fly attack.
2. Improved control of olive fly pest through anticipation of pest attacks and application of treatments during early stages of the fly lifecycle.
3. Efficient management of phytosanitary treatments, by applying them when more effective and by avoiding them when not needed, thus reducing environmental damage.

Glossary

Agroecosystem analysis: holistic approach required to analyze the complexity of agricultural systems that considers aspects from ecology, sociology, economics and politics (e.g. in the form of agro-technical inputs, invasive species, climate change...)

Numerical modelling: a computer model that is designed to simulate and reproduce the mechanisms of a particular system

Climate pattern: a calculated value or profile used to describe the state and changes in the climate system

Number of annual and spring heat days: count of days with maximum temperature above 28°C per year and in spring

Climate projections: probabilistic estimates of climate variables that extend well into the future (long-term), from decades up to the end of the century

Number of annual dry days: count of days with precipitation below 2 mm per year

Climate services: transformation of climate-related data and other information into customized products such as trends, economic analysis, advice on best practices, and any other climate-related service liable to benefit that may be of use for the society

Number of winter cold days: count of days with minimum temperature below -7°C in winter

Seasonal predictions: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables for the next season (up to 6 months)

Mean summer maximum temperature: average daily maximum air temperature during summer

Total annual, summer and winter precipitation: total amount of rainfall per year, in summer and in winter

Mean winter minimum temperature: average daily minimum air temperature during winter

Weather forecasts: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables for the next hours and days (up to two weeks)

About MED-GOLD

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Figure 4-14. Olive/olive oil infosheet

CLIMATE SERVICES FOR THE DURUM WHEAT AND PASTA SECTOR

"Facing climate change is amongst the greatest challenges of our times" Chiara Monotti, Barilla G&R Fratelli SPA

Durum wheat, and thus, pasta production is influenced by weather and climate conditions and is highly affected by climate extremes. Thereby, its vulnerability and exposure as well as the potential adaptation strategies under changing climate conditions must be assessed. MED-GOLD will use agro-climatic services deploying climate information at the medium (next 6-13 months) and long-term (2-30 years). To provide the highest value for decision-making, the services will be co-developed with professional users from the sector.

Durum wheat producers face diverse challenges affecting several decision processes in their business, such as agro-management and stock management and strategic decisions. Some examples are presented below to show how climate services - in this case, predictions of climate variables and bioclimatic indices - can support critical decisions along the durum wheat food chain and win over challenges posed by climate variability and climate change.

Time scale	Decision type	Challenges	MED-GOLD climate service	Benefits
Mid-term (e.g., 6-13 months)	Agro-management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better planning of soil tillage, fertilization, crop protection treatment and weed management Improve choice of variety and density at sowing Higher accuracy with sowing and harvest setting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wheat phenological development Temperature Precipitation Hydrological balance Heavy rain during winter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimize exposure to weather extremes Cost reduction through optimal fertilization and agro-management planning Maximize crop yield and quality Optimize use of fertilizers
	Stock management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better contracts and price Better planning of supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Useful rain for fertiliser activation Frost risk index Heat stress index 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better planning of supply chain, contracts and prices
Long-term (e.g., up to 30 years)	Long-term strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Selection of future new cultivation areas Choice of new varieties, breeding and genetic improvement activities Monitoring of new pests, pathogens, weeds Anticipation of purchase needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Projected yield changes Projected risk of climate extremes (i.e., heat stress, drought in critical phenological phases...) Projected risk of quality and nutritional issues Feasible adaptation strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicate suitable cultivation areas Better estimation of production for market and food security Improve regional policy planning and development, national adaptation strategies and EU policies (e.g. CAP) Match adequate varieties to expected climate Prepare for crop protection and prevention of invasive species Better use of investments (e.g., machinery, irrigation)

Planning of fertilizers' application

Fertilizers are essential for the plant growth. The amount of nitrogen to be applied, the intervention timings and the form of nitrogen to be distributed are mainly influenced by the soil characteristics, the wheat variety and the climate in the cropping season (mainly temperature and precipitation, which drive the effect of fertilizers on the crop). Nitrogen can be distributed to crops in two forms: nitric nitrogen (NO₃⁻), or ammoniacal nitrogen (NH₄⁺). Nitric nitrogen can be readily used by plants and it does not bind to soil particles, so it is more prone to leaching. On the contrary, ammoniacal nitrogen needs to be transformed in nitric nitrogen by the action of bacteria in the soil in order to be used by the plants, and it can bound to soil and humus particles, so that it is less readily available to plants and it is not subject to leaching.

Currently, farmers including those in the BARILLA (MED-GOLD champion user for the durum wheat sector) supply chain, do the first nitrogen application during tillering. This is particularly important for crops grown in poor soils, especially after periods of high rain and low temperatures (it should be limited in case of mild weather and low rains). The second application of nitrogen fertilizers takes place at the beginning of the stem elongation, making nitrogen available during the most demanding period for the crop and setting the base for the quality of the grains. The last application is done at booting, with effects on both potential production and grain quality in terms of proteins.

Advantages of having access to seasonal climate predictions:

1. Improved choice of the type of nitrogen fertiliser in order to optimise plant uptake and reduce losses (i.e. leaching)
2. Better anticipation and planning of fertilizers' application enhancing cost reduction
3. Efficient stock management accounting in advance for the fertilizers to be used

Glossary

Climate predictions: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables that extend further into the future than weather forecasts, from months and seasons up to decade

Climate projections: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables that extend even further into the future than climate predictions, from decades up to centuries

Climate services: transformation of climate-related data and other information into customized products such as trends, economic analysis, advice on best practices, and any other climate-related service liable to benefit that may be of use for the society

Frost risk index: number of days with minimum temperature below 2°C from wheat heading to end of flowering

Heat stress index: number of hot days with maximum daily temperature above 28 °C between wheat heading to the end of grain filling period

Heavy rain during winter: number of days with cumulate rainfall above 40 mm

Hydrological balance: Standardized Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) calculated for several time intervals linked to wheat phenology

Seasonal predictions: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables for the next season (up to 6 months)

Useful rain for fertilizer activation: number of days with rainfall above 10 mm during wheat tillering

About MED-GOLD

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Figure 4-15. Durum wheat/pasta infosheet

4.1.6. MED-GOLD WEBINAR

The first webinar was performed on the 15th January 2019 entitled "Climate services as drivers of value into the Mediterranean wine sector". This webinar (Figure 4-16) was presented in Portuguese language and mainly focused on the grape-wine sector, for which MED-GOLD has a pilot site in Portugal.

Figure 4-16. MED-GOLD grape-wine webinar

4.1.7. MED-GOLD EVENTS

Table 4-2 summarizes the events that have been organized during the second year of the project by different partners addressed to both internal and external project members. Photographs from some of the events are shown in Figure 4-17.

During 2019, several focus groups for each sector were organised. In general, most of the participants agreed on the usefulness of climate services for their respective sectors.

Figure 4-17. Pictures of the events

In addition to the workshops, the second MED-GOLD General Assembly took place in Cagliari (Italy) from October 15th to 17th. During this event, the stakeholder workshop “Climate Change adaptation in Mediterranean Agriculture” (Figure 4-18), organized by Beetobit and ENEA, was presented. The attendees counted with several profiles among farmers, researchers, students, and public and private representation.

Figure 4-18. Workshop during MED-GOLD General Assembly

Table 4-2. List of MED-GOLD events performed.

ID	Organiser	Name	Date	Location	Description	Attendees
1	ENEA	MED-GOLD workshop on the user perspective of seasonal forecasts	11/02/2019	Brussels (Belgium)	A workshop organised by the H2020 project MED-GOLD aims to ensure mutual understanding between climate scientists and farmers to achieve a successful development of climate services for agriculture.	MED-GOLD partners
2	BARILLA	Second MED-GOLD workshop on durum wheat: supporting strategic decisions	15/05/2019	Parma (Italy)	The MED-GOLD team presented a beta version of new tools to support strategic decisions in the durum wheat/pasta sector during a workshop held at the headquarters of the Barilla food company in Parma, Italy.	10 participants overall, including durum wheat farmers, producers' associations and elevators across different Italian regions, as well as technical experts from local political institutions, breeding, and stocks exchange markets
6	DCOOP	MED-GOLD focus group on the sectorial tools for olives and the olive oil sector	09/05/2019	Antequera (Spain)	The MED-GOLD project presented a beta version of the tool designed for the olive/olive oil sector during a focus group meeting	The focus group meeting consisted of three technical sessions and a last session on conclusions, in which the participants discussed the proposed tools. The event was attended by 4 participants from DCOOP, representing the whole value chain of the olive sector in the main olive producing areas of Andalusia (Spain), and by several scientific and technical experts from the MED-GOLD team.
13	SOGRAPE	MED-GOLD workshop to discuss climate services tools for the wine sector	27/05/2019	Porto (Portugal)	The workshop had the objective to discuss, together with users, the climate services tools developed for grapes and the wine sector. This event was a follow-up from a previous focus group organised a year ago at the same venue, to discuss climate knowledge necessary to support decision making for wine production.	The workshop was attended by 12 participants from different areas of the company, including the departments of oenology, viticulture, human resources, project management, hosting and public relations, innovation, quality and safety, property maintenance and general service.
3	BEETOBIT, ENEA	2 nd General Assembly	15/10/2019	Cagliari (Italy)	General Assembly – Workshop Climate Change adaptation in Mediterranean Agriculture (translated from Italian).	MED-GOLD partners. The workshop counted with the participation of 40 attendees with several profiles: agro-alimentary sector, researchers, students and public and private sectors.

4.1.8. PRESS RELEASES & NEWS

Table 4-3. List of MED-GOLD press releases and news published during the second year (M13-M24)

Partner Id	Partner	Date	Sector	Target Group	ROI	Title	Site	Link
4	BSC	05/11/2018	ALL	ALL	EUROPE	MED-GOLD European project on climate threats to the agricultural sector	Article on the MED-GOLD website	https://bit.ly/2It3Gin
8	GMV	07/11/2018	ALL	ALL	GLOBAL	The H2020 MED-GOLD project holds its first general assembly	MED-GOLD website	https://bit.ly/2IX2xzK
13	SOGRAPE	20/11/2018	ALL	ALL	PT	Sogrape recebe 1.ª assembleia-geral do projecto europeu Med-Gold em Vila Nova de Gaia	Agricultura e mar - a magazine	https://bit.ly/2lrWxPb
13	SOGRAPE	22/11/2018	ALL	ALL	PT	Sogrape acolheu assembleia-geral do projecto europeu MED-GOLD	Frutas Legumes e Flores Magazine	https://bit.ly/2IP8Mp4
4	BSC	01/12/2018	ALL	END-USERS	GLOBAL	1st MED-GOLD Newsletter	Project newsletter	https://bit.ly/2It3SOD
13	SOGRAPE	01/01/2019	GRAPE	INDUSTRY-INTERMEDIATE	GLOBAL	MED- GOLD: prever o clima para melhorar a gestão vitivinícola	Company internal magazine article - page 13	https://bit.ly/2kfx2k4
4	BSC	13/02/2019	ALL	ALL	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD workshop on the user perspective of seasonal forecasts	Article on the MED-GOLD website	https://bit.ly/2XcwJVI
	ENEA / BSC	13/03/2019	ALL	GP	GLOBAL	One year of MED-GOLD: Interview with the coordinators	Interview on the MED-GOLD website	https://bit.ly/2koZK1N
13	SOGRAPE	15/03/2019	GRAPE	GP	PT	Fighting climate change in the wine sector (PT)	MED-GOLD mention in news article	https://bit.ly/2jWF697
6	DCOOP	09/05/2019	OLIVE	GP	SP	Getting that other medias publish the news.	News of the Olive Focus Group	https://bit.ly/2IX1QXb
6	DCOOP	10/05/2019	OLIVE	GP	SP	Dcoop celebra un Grupo Focal para evaluar la herramienta para el olivar diseñada por Med-Gold	20 minutes press	https://bit.ly/2jXaHr8
6	DCOOP	10/05/2019	OLIVE	GP	SP	Dcoop participa en el diseño de una herramienta para predecir la evolución de la plaga de la mosca del olivo	Diario Sur press	https://bit.ly/2kqt5ce
6	DCOOP	10/05/2019	OLIVE	GP	SP	Dcoop celebra un Grupo Focal para evaluar la herramienta para el olivar diseñada por Med-Gold	Europress	https://bit.ly/2jUt5Rq
1	ENEA	15/05/2019	DURUM WHEAT	GP	EUROPE	Second MED-GOLD workshop on durum wheat: supporting strategic decisions	MEDGOLD website	https://bit.ly/2kq0W52
9	HORTA	24/05/2019	ALL	END-USERS	IT	MED-GOLD brief description and information on subscription to the community	Horta website	https://bit.ly/2krHV1Z
4	BSC	31/05/2019	OLIVE	GP	SP	MED-GOLD focus group on the sectorial tools for olives and the olive oil sector	Article on the MED-GOLD website	https://bit.ly/2kp0fJd
4	BSC	20/06/2019	GRAPE	GP	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD workshop to discuss climate services tools for the wine sector	Article on the MED-GOLD website	https://bit.ly/2kgzBCr
	UMNG	01/01/2019	COFFEE	GP	CO	Docentes Neogranadinos en Proyecto MED-GOLD	Note in University Newspaper	https://bit.ly/2MxZnx5

4.1.9. PARTICIPATION IN CONFERENCES, WORKSHOPS AND EVENTS

Table 4-4. List of events in which MED-GOLD partners have participated during second year (M13-M24)

Partner Id	Partner	Event	Date	Sector	Target Group	ROI	Activity	Link
13	SOGRAPE	CONF	19/11/2018	GRAPE	INSTITUTIONS	GLOBAL	41st. World Congress of Vine and Wine	https://bit.ly/2IU1ujX
13	SOGRAPE	WS	29/10/2018	GRAPE	ALL	PT	MED-GOLD Stakeholder workshop - Portugal	
13	SOGRAPE	CONF	22/11/2018	CLIMATE	ALL	PT	CLIMA 2018 - Congresso Nacional sobre Alterações Climáticas	
1	ENEA	CONF	27/11/2018	GRAPE	ALL	GLOBAL	10th World Bulk Wine Exhibition in Amsterdam, The Netherlands	https://bit.ly/2IS7HwM
4	BSC	CONF	05/12/2018	CLIMATE	ALL	GLOBAL	Participation in a joint session at COP 24	https://bit.ly/2IS9O3G
15	UNIVLEEDS	WS	12/12/2018	ALL	INSTITUTIONS	EUROPE	Agrisource European Workshop	https://bit.ly/2ltznrQ
13	SOGRAPE	WS	08/02/2019	GRAPE	END-USERS	IT	Presentation «We can't trust in our grandfathers anymore?» - slide about MED-GOLD	https://bit.ly/2lVN7vE
1	ENEA	WS	11/02/2019	ALL	ALL	GLOBAL	User expectations on seasonal forecasts in agriculture	
1	ENEA	WS	13/02/2019	CLIMATE	INDUSTRY-INTERMEDIATE	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD workshop on the user perspective of seasonal forecasts	https://bit.ly/2XcwJVl
13	SOGRAPE	CONF	06/03/2019	GRAPE	GENERAL PUBLIC	GLOBAL	Presentation «Vineyards responses around the world»	https://bit.ly/2jZFEer
4	BSC	WS	19/03/2019	CLIMATE	ACADEMIA	GLOBAL	Workshop on communication, visualisation and user engagement within the COST inDust project, Bucharest (RO)	https://bit.ly/2lOYXrc
4	BSC	WS	09/04/2019	ALL	INSTITUTIONS	GLOBAL	Presentation in workshop on climate change impact on agriculture, Barcelona	https://bit.ly/2k1gA6O
1	ENEA	CONF	10/04/2019	ALL	ACADEMIA	EUROPE	Oral presentation at European Geophysical Union General Assembly 2019, Vienna, Austria	https://www.egu2019.eu/
	ENEA/BEEBOBIT	MEETING	08/05/2019	ALL	INSTITUTIONS	EUROPE	Talk in ECMWF to present MED-GOLD and ICT platform	
13	SOGRAPE	CONF	13/05/2019	GRAPE	ACADEMIA	GLOBAL	Oral presentation at the Oenoviti Symposium, Athens, Greece	https://bit.ly/2lVG4mD
13	SOGRAPE	CONF	15/05/2019	GRAPE	END-USERS	PT	11º Simpósio de Vitivinicultura do Alentejo	https://bit.ly/2kqjuSK
6	DCOOP	MEETING	15/05/2019	OLIVE	END-USERS	SPAIN	Distributing brochures among the visitors of EXPOLIVA (fair of the olive sector). Explanation of MED-GOLD to people who were interested in it.	https://bit.ly/2VfYFWz
1	ENEA	MEETING	17/05/2019	ALL	ACADEMIA	EUROPE	presentation of MED-GOLD Activities in GA 2019 of MEDSCOPE project (Milan, Italy)	https://bit.ly/2mcPOcn
15	UNIVLEEDS	MEETING	18/05/2019	OLIVE	END-USERS	ITALY	Online presentation at Masters of Olive Oil International contest, San Remo, Italy	https://bit.ly/2kf30gf
	UNIVLEEDS/BSC	CONF	29/05/2019	ALL	ACADEMIA	EUROPE	Climate & Climateurope booth at ECCA and distribution of brochures	https://www.ecca2019.eu
15	UNIVLEEDS	CONF	30/05/2019	ALL	ACADEMIA	EUROPE	Oral presentation at European Climate Change Adaptation, Lisbon, Greece	https://www.ecca2019.eu
12	NOA	CONF	24/06/2019	OLIVE	ACADEMIA	SP	Oral presentation at the Adapt2Clima conference, Heraklion, 24-25 June 2019, Greece	https://bit.ly/2WFq4mf
	CREA	CONF	24/06/2019	AGRO	GENERAL PUBLIC	GLOBAL	Oral presentation by CREA "Agroforestry models overestimate photosynthesis of understory crops"	https://afta2019.org/
12	NOA	MEETING	09/09/2019	CLIMATE	GENERAL PUBLIC	EUROPE	Poster presentation by NOA "Mediterranean agro-climate projections and the case of olives in Andalucia: results from the MED-GOLD project"	https://bit.ly/2m8khrP

4.1.10. UPCOMING EVENTS OR MATERIAL

MED-GOLD project is focused in the communication and dissemination of the project and its scope using different channels. The following activities are being prepared by the MED-GOLD team.

- MED-GOLD Summer School 2020: This workshop is being prepared. Two coordination meetings have taken place and a first proposal related to organization (thematic, dates, locations, profile attendees, etc.) was launched. These meetings took place on 15th July and 20th July.
- Next Newsletter will be published in December 2019
- Infosheet on climate services for the coffee sector is under development (October 2019)

4.1.11. INTERACTION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

Dissemination synergies with other EU initiatives such as Climate-KIC, JPI Climate, FACE-JPI, JPI Water and related ERA-NET (e.g. ERA-NET on Climate Services) as well as clustering with other climate service related EC funded projects via H2020 or other complementary programmes (i.e. LIFE, Copernicus, PRIMA, etc.) has been explored during this first year of the project's life. Deliverable 6.1 "Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report n.1" summarised those interactions [RD.4].

Actually, MED-GOLD is working with 14 Climate Services Initiatives (Table 4-5) and 8 initiatives related with agriculture services (Table 4-6).

Table 4-5. Description of each initiative related to Climate Services

Initiative	Type	Description	MED-GOLD Contact	Link
AgriCLASS project	Copernicus	This project provides agricultural climate advisory services. The AgriCLASS Sectoral Information System will take available, high-quality climate data and agricultural data and models, and translate them into products that prove useful to the agricultural sector. The concept is to build a system which allows climate variables to be fused with agricultural information.	Met Office	https://bit.ly/2kh5g6w
CLARA	H2020	Stakeholder engagements: agricultural case study community; new techniques for assessing the added value of climate services to be applied in MED-GOLD		http://www.clara-project.eu/
Climateurope	H2020	Coordination and support action that pursues synergies with other EU initiatives through a Europe-wide network for researchers, suppliers and users of climate information	Met Office, BSC, SOGRAPE	https://bit.ly/2KH04AJ
Climate-KIC		Climate-KIC is a European knowledge and innovation community, working to accelerate the transition to a zero-carbon economy. Supported by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT). Also coordinates MARCO	ENEA	http://www.climate-kic.org/
Copernicus		A project funded by the European Commission designed to support society by providing authoritative information about the past, present and future climate for adaptation and mitigation purposes by providing consistent and authoritative information about climate change. Their Climate Data Store offers free and open access to climate data and tools.	Met Office	http://www.copernicus.eu/
EU-MACS	H2020	EU-MACS is concerned with market research for climate services. Their goal is to improve matching of supply with demand for climate services products and make climate information more accessible.	ENEA	http://eu-macs.eu/eu-macs/
Indecis	ERA4CS/ ERA-NET/ JPI	Indecis is concerned with the development across Europe of user-oriented climate indicators for GFCS high-priority sectors: agriculture, disaster risk reduction, energy, health, water and tourism	ENEA, BSC	
MARCO	H2020	MARCO is concerned with market research for climate services. Coordinated by the European Climate-KIC, it gathers market research firms, climate scientists, climate services practitioners and innovation actors to provide detailed insight into the climate services market in Europe.	ENEA	http://marco-h2020.eu/

MEDSCOPE	ERA4CS	MEDSCOPE is working on optimisation of seasonal forecasts of Mediterranean region, this is possibly of interest for MED-GOLD	BSC	https://www.medscope-project.eu/
PRIMAVERA	H2020	PRIMAVERA aims to develop a new generation of advanced and well-evaluated high-resolution global climate models, capable of simulating and predicting regional climate with unprecedented fidelity, for the benefit of governments, business and society in general.	Met Office, BSC	https://www.primavera-h2020.eu/
S2S4E	H2020	S2S4E will offer an innovative service to improve renewable energy (RE) variability management by developing new research methods exploring the frontiers of weather conditions for future weeks and months.	BSC	https://www.s2s4e.eu/
SECLI-FIRM	H2020	The central objective of SECLI-FIRM is to demonstrate how the use of improved climate forecasts, out to several months ahead, can add practical and economic value to decision-making processes and outcomes, primarily in the energy sector, but also in the water sector.	Met Office	http://www.secli-firm.eu/
Task Force on evaluation of climate services from users' perspective	Trans-projects voluntary initiative led by CMCC	This Task Force will explore synergies and common methodological grounds across the various projects, identify and share best practice examples, and elaborate a set of minimum requirements that the users' assessments of climate services should meet.	ENEA, BSC, SOGRAPE, UNILEEDS	
VISCA	H2020	VISCA is a project providing a climate service and decision support system integrating climate. Agricultural and end-user requirements to design medium to long-term adaptation strategies to climate change.	BSC	http://visca.eu/

Table 4-6. Description of each initiative related to Agriculture Services

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	MED-GOLD Contact	Link
ADAPT2CLIMA	LIFE	The main aim of LIFE ADAPT2CLIMA project is to increase knowledge on the vulnerability of EU Mediterranean agriculture to climate change and to support decision making for adaptation planning. The methodology is based on the deployment of a set of climate, hydrological and crop simulation models for the assessment of climate change impacts on agriculture, as well as, on the development of a decision support tool for the elaboration of adaptation strategies for the agricultural sector.	Ongoing	NOA	http://adapt2clima.eu
Agrisource		Agrisource is a project carried out by two French research organisations, INRA and CIRAD, and funded by the European Climate-KIC. Agrisource is an open online platform for agriculture. Its content is provided by its worldwide community, and highlights all ideas, projects, innovation that in some way contribute to the achievement of two high stake objectives: Mitigating green-house gas (GHG) emissions Adapting to climate change	Ongoing	UNIVLEEDS	https://bit.ly/32n0pRj
BeFOre		This projects' aim is to establish a multi-lateral network of research and innovation staff active in OLIVE germplasm access, conservation, evaluation and exploitation. Strengthening research capacities through the exchange of knowledge and expertise on a shared research programme focused on establishing integrated common protocols to phenotype and characterize plants at molecular, morphological and	Ongoing	ENEA	http://www.beforeproject.eu/

		physiological level, and evaluating the olive oil quality related to varieties.			
CLIMALERT ERA4CS	JPI	Part of JPI Climate - this is a Climate Alert Smart System for Sustainable Water and Agriculture	Ongoing	SOGRAPE	https://bit.ly/2keByPw
DOUROZONE		Supported by the Portuguese National Foundation for Science and Technology. This project aims to evaluate the risk of ozone exposure for vineyards of Douro Wine Region under present and future climate scenarios. There are potential bidirectional interactions with MED-GOLD.	Ongoing	SOGRAPE	http://dourozone.web.ua.pt/
IMPREX	H2020	This project aims to enhance forecast quality of extreme hydro-meteorological conditions and their impacts. MED-GOLD is interested in any agriculture and drought case studies they might produce.	Ongoing	BSC	http://impres.eu/
MACSUR	JPI	A knowledge hub of FACCE-JPI. Its main goal is to develop pan-European capability in development, use and interpretation of models for risk assessments of climate change impacts on European agriculture.	Finished	ENEA	https://macsur.eu/about
PRIMA		Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA) A joint programme focused on the development and application of solutions for food systems and water resources in the Mediterranean basin.	Ongoing	ENEA	https://bit.ly/1VKzMfM
PEFMED	Interreg MED Programme	The overall objective of the PEFMED project is to test the applicability of the new EU Product Environmental Footprint method (PEF) for some specific product groups in Mediterranean agrofood regional systems from Mediterranean Countries (Italy, Spain, France, Portugal, Greece and Slovenia) and the following product groups: dairy, meat, olive oil, wine, feed, packaged water.	Ongoing	ENEA	https://pefmed.interreg-med.eu/

Table 4-7. Potential initiatives contacted

Initiative	Type	Description
CLARITY	H2020	CLARITY will provide an operational eco-system of cloud-based climate services to calculate and present the expected effects of CC-induced and -amplified hazards at the level of risk, vulnerability and impact functions. CLARITY will offer what-if decision support functions to investigate the effects of adaptation measures and risk reduction options in the specific project context and allow the comparison of alternative strategies.
EUSTACE	H2020	EUSTACE is using surface skin temperature from satellites to estimate daily air temperature everywhere. This data is of possible interest for MED-GOLD.
Grow Observatory	H2020	This project is addressing science challenges and data gaps, from creating soil maps to enhancing climate prediction models and earth observation from satellites.
JPI Water	JPI	http://www.waterjpi.eu/
JPI Climate	JPI	http://www.jpi-climate.eu/home
LANDMARK Project	H2020	LANDMARK is a European research project on the sustainable management of land and soil in Europe. The questions that the project addresses are: "How can we make the most of our land ? How can we ensure that our soils deliver on the many expectations we have of our land ?"
NEREUS		As Network of European Regions Using Space Technologies, NEREUS offers a dynamic platform to all Regions aiming at making a better use of space applications for the delivery of efficient public policies benefiting citizens.
PROSNOW		The PROSNOW project ambitions to build a demonstrator of a meteorological and climate prediction system from one week to several months ahead applied to snow management, specifically tailored to the needs of the ski industry using a co-design approach. This novel climate service holds significant potential to increase the resilience of socio-economic mountain stakeholders and supports their real-time climate change adaptation potential.

PUCS	H2020	PUCS aims at a genuine market uptake of (urban) climate services, based on a distributed network of local business intermediaries throughout Europe, enhancing the awareness for urban climate-related issues in the end-user community, and converting (mature) research results into tailored added-value information, thus removing important barriers for the deployment of urban climate services.
XF-ACTORS	H2020	The first project in Europe entirely devoted to research on <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i> .
Adviclim	LIFE	R&D project aims to study and develop climate change adaptation and mitigation scenarios at vineyard scale in European wine regions.
AgMIP	Global UK/US government funded initiative	Major international effort linking the climate, crop, and economic modelling communities supported by UK Department for International Development's UKaid, in partnership with the US Department of Agriculture Agricultural Research Service
Agri Adapt	LIFE	This project aims to demonstrate how sustainable adaptation measures can help livestock, arable and permanent crop farms become more climate resilient.
EUCLID		The overall objective is to secure food production for the increasing worldwide population while developing sustainable production methodologies to fight pests with an Integrated Pest Management approach (IPM), to be used in European and Chinese agriculture.
FACCEJPI	JPI	The Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change (FACCE-JPI) brings together 24 countries who are committed to building an integrated European Research Area addressing the interconnected challenges of sustainable agriculture, food security and impacts of climate change.
LIFE	LIFE	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/about/index.htm
OIV (International Organisation of Vine and Wine)		World scientific and technical reference organisation of vine and wine, made up of 47 member states. This organisation holds world congresses of vine and wine.
OLIVE4CLIMATE	LIFE	The project will test and verify innovative approaches and demonstrative actions aimed at the implementation of climate change mitigation strategies linked to the olive oil supply chain.
OLIVECLIMA project		Investigating the introduction of new olive crop management
OLIVE-MIRACLE	JPI	(FACCE SURPLUS, part of the FACCE JPI program) Modelling solutions for Improved and Resilient mAnagement strategies for Olive tree against future CLimatE change
PURE		The overall objective of this activity was to design more robust IPM solutions to implement not only in high-tech greenhouse systems.
SolACE	H2020	The goal of SolACE - Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use - is to help European agriculture face major challenges, notably increased rainfall variability and reduced use of N and P fertilizers.
SusCrop ERA_NET	H2020	ERA-Net Cofund Action, which aims to strengthen the European Research Area (ERA) in the field of Sustainable Crop Production
SusFoodERA_NET	H2020	SUSFOOD2: The #H2020 ERA-NET CoFund on sustainable Food Production and Consumption.
WHEAT	CGIAR	WHEAT is a global alliance unparalleled in the history of wheat research. WHEAT is a CGIAR Research Program launched in 2012 and led by the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT)

Due to interaction with other initiatives, MED GOLD has been reported on the Climateurope website (Figure 4-18) in the stories section, at this hyperlink:

<https://www.climateurope.eu/med-gold-turning-climate-related-information-into-added-value-for-traditional-mediterranean-g-rape-ol-ive-and-d-urum-wheat-food-systems/>

Figure 4-19. MED-GOLD reported in other initiatives website

4.1.12. MED-GOLD GAZETTE

Internal blog where relevant events in the life of MED-GOLD project are summarised to help partners to stay on track (Figure 4-19). It is published quarterly.

Figure 4-20. MED-GOLD GAZETTE on the project wiki.

5. CONTACT WITH THE POLICY COMMUNITY

Considering that MED-GOLD project aims to provide valuable information that allows to decision makers to take actions against the climate change. In the particular case of MED-GOLD the focus is leaded to agriculture sector.

As described in RD.2 the MED-GOLD strategy for engaging the policy community defines both short-term and long-term actions with a two-fold aim:

- Inform the policy community about the project and its relevance for the agriculture sector
- Getting informed/receive feedback about what are the policy needs regarding climate information and services

During 2019 the engagement activities focused to policy community reached the following results:

1. MED GOLD Partner: **BSC**
 - a. Date: 17/10/2018
 - b. Type Of Interaction: Attend the event "From linear to circular - How R&I can transform the future of food systems" (roundtable format)
 - c. Main Discussion Topics: Topic 1: Framing the critical policy questions and challenges to be addressed in Horizon Europe and beyond, and the strategic rationale for EU ambitions in the domain. Topic2: Exploring how circular economy-based research and innovation can transform current strategies, business models and partnerships to achieve sustainable food futures. Topic 3: Identifying the highest potential areas for R&I investment into breakthrough science and technologies throughout food value chains. Open discussion to gather latest insights recommendations from participants to start shaping the thematic framework and action plan.
2. MED GOLD Partner: **BSC**
 - a. Organization: Union for the Mediterranean (UFM) and RTD
 - b. Contact Profile: Policy officer RTD-EC and Senior Climate Adviser/ Energy Climate Action at UFM
 - c. Date: 14/03/2019
 - d. Type Of Interaction: Invited to present the work done in different projects
3. MED GOLD Partner: **BSC**
 - a. Organization: Union for the Mediterranean (UFM)
 - b. Contact Profile: Not a specific person - UFM: intergovernmental institution bringing together the 28 European Union Member States and 15 countries from the Southern and Eastern shores of the Mediterranean to promote dialogue and cooperation
 - c. Date: 09/04/2019
 - d. Type Of Interaction: After the previous meeting with UFM & RTD, we were invited to have a presentation in a workshop on climate change impact on agriculture in Barcelona
 - e. Main Discussion Topics: Presentation about climate innovation and how climate services can help societies to develop and better adapt to climate variability and change
4. MED GOLD Partner: **BSC**
 - a. Organization: DG Clima
 - b. Contact Profile: Policy officer DG Clima and Deputy Head of Unit for Better Regulation in the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
 - c. Date: 15/05/2019
 - d. Type Of Interaction: Invitation to present the work done in different projects
 - e. Main Discussion Topics: General discussion about the work done in different climate services related projects
5. MED GOLD Partner: **BSC**
 - a. Organization: COPA-COGECA
 - b. Contact Profile: Policy advisor and project officer/ policy advisor for wine and olive sector
 - c. Date: 1/7/2019

- d. Type Of Interaction: Online meeting 16 July 2019
 - e. Main Discussion Topics: Contribution of climate services more in economic terms than in policy issues. Digitalisation and how to provide services. Replicability of MED-GOLD tools to other crops, other regions, other crop systems. Suggestions to contact to INRA/ France Agrimer/ national and voluntary environmental schemes. Directives: fertilizers, water, soils and data management.
6. MED GOLD Partner: **BSC**
- a. Organization: Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fishing and Food
 - b. Contact Profile: Subdelegation of herbaceous cultures and olive oil
 - c. Date: 19/08/2019
 - d. Type Of Interaction: Online meeting. Suggestions they have made by telephone: contact the delegation on fruits and viticulture of the same General Direction and contact the Oficina Española de Cambio Climático
 - e. Main Discussion Topics: Relevance of MED-GOLD results for agricultural insurance policies. Suggestion to the contact ENESA (Entidad Nacional de Seguros Agrarios) an autonomous organism that depends on the Ministry of Agriculture and that is working directly with Agroseguros.
- Connection with the research on new varieties able to resist the adverse effects of climate change and increase resilience. Some countries use information on yield predictions to anticipate production risks. In the case of Spain, the Ministry has the intention to incorporate this type of information. The Ministry of Ecological Transition has developed a visualization platform with information on climate change scenarios.
- Suggested contact: Oficina Española de Cambio Climático, which have developed the national plan to adapt to Climate Change.
7. MED GOLD Partner: **ENEA**
- a. Organization: Comité Européen des Entreprises Vins (CEEV)
 - b. Contact Profile: Secretary General Strategic orientation, Representation, Press relations, Daily management
 - c. Date 16/10/2019
 - d. Type of Interaction: Gave an invited talk during the MED-GOLD General Assembly. Idea to contact him again later on in the project
 - e. Main Discussion Topics: During his talk, he mentioned that advice to policy-makers is mostly focused in 4 areas: (i) adaptation to climate change, (ii) plant protection, (iii) genetic resources and (iv) consumption, and that priorities i and ii can be addressed by MED-GOLD
8. MED GOLD Partner: **BSC**
- a. Organization: Catalan Water Agency (ACA)
 - b. Contact Profile: Department of Water Management, Area of Water Supply, Catalan Water Agency
 - c. Date: 01/07/2017 (interview developed in the framework of the IMPREX project, but results can also be useful for MED-GOLD)
 - d. Type Of Interaction: face-to-face interview
 - e. Main Discussion Topics: Improvement of climate predictions for better estimation of reservoir water volumes and better water allocation for agriculture - for the ACA Special Drought Plan (Pla especial de sequera)

Another policy members were contacted during this period highlighting that any response was obtained.

The strategy adopted by MED-GOLD has identified some entry points to the policy community as well as the participation in relevant events in 2020.

6. CONCLUSIONS

During its second year (M13-M24), the MED-GOLD project has developed several activities focused on increasing the interest of stakeholders and the general public and showing how climate-related information is relevant for decision making directed to increase the productivity of crops, particularly for traditional Mediterranean olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta systems. The effort to create a communication platform that combines information on workshops, seminars, news, interactions in social media (e.g., tweets) and publications (e.g., infosheets) has been considerable.

The creation of a visual identify as well as an important emphasis on the language component, including material translations, demonstrates a strong interest in increasing the number of registered MED-GOLD community members.

Some of the topics that need to be reinforced relate to increasing the number of followers on social networks and to engage stakeholders as an active part of the project using all channels available for this goal.

The table 6-1 summarizes the main metrics based on the results exposed above.

Table 6-1. Summary of MED-GOLD communication and dissemination activities

Metrics	Figure
Number of organized workshops (includes both participations in events and own events)	12
Average number of participants in events	19
Number of MED-GOLD community members	152
Number of infosheets published	3
Number of newsletters	2
Number of publications in media	62
Number of presentations in conferences, meetings and congresses	24
Initiatives contacted	47
Date: 5 th November, 2019	

Figure 6-1. Evolution of MED-GOLD C&D activities.

More attention should be paid in the following years to increase the impact and the number of MED-GOLD community members once the infrastructure and content has been generated (climate services tools, platform, demonstrators, replicability, etc.). In this sense, the MED-GOLD consortium is working on developing new materials based on the latest advances to increase the project's impact. Increasing the number of contacted initiatives including also initiatives beyond the European sphere is under discussion.

END OF DOCUMENT

